

High-speed X-ray multi-projection and ultra high-speed radiography imaging to capture transverse cracking in glass fibre-reinforced composites

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Composite materials group

Transverse cracking in composites

Tensile loading

loading rate ↓

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crack propagation speed ↓

Imaging transverse cracking

3D crack shape

Labscale

XCT

2.9 μm

Post-mortem

Cracks

Synchrotron

Fast synchrotron radiation CT (4D-CT)

Garcea et al. (2017).

1 Hz + 1.1 μm

Rotation stage

2D crack evolution

Radiography

10 Hz + 49.5 μm

Lack of contrast

Crack opening

X-ray phase contrast imaging

Pournoori et al. (2023).

Damage onset

Final crack

1 MHz + 15.2 μm

Triggering strategy

X-ray multi-projection imaging (XMPI)

X-ray tomography requires rotation of the sample

Rotation-free simultaneous projections through XMPI

Yao et al. (2025)

XMPI at ID19

kHz acquisition-speed camera (Photron Nova)

Scintillator + 90° mirror

Detectors

Perfect crystal in Bragg or Laue configuration

Beam-splitter

Loading rig

Composite specimen

Ge-111

Sequential damage features imaged at 3 kHz

500 μm

1. Transverse crack
2. Transverse crack
3. Further crack opening
4. Delaminations
5. Final failure 0° plies

Frame subtraction

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Transverse cracking
58 % UTS

Final failure imaged at 10 kHz

Fast 2D X-ray imaging - Trigger

Goal: Capture crack propagation in 2D up to MHz

Trigger:

- Ultra-short time lapses (256 μ s at 1 MHz)
- Non-repetitive event
- Experiment 30 s

Option 1: Conductive coating

Option 2: Signal from load drop

Radiography at ForMAX

MHz acquisition-speed camera
(HPV-X2, Shimadzu)

Microscope
Scintillator + 90° mirror

Detector

1 MHz: 256 μ s
vs.
Human reaction
time: 250 ms

Trigger

Loading rig

□
FOV
2.6×1.6 mm²

5 mm

Composite
specimen

Rotation/translation
stages

Final failure near transverse crack

100 kHz (played 1666x slower)

20 kHz (played 333x slower)

Beam-induced sample degradation

Softened matrix

Thermal degradation

Heat load

[90,0,90] 10 s at 20 keV with natural convection in tube with slots

Irradiation glass-epoxy OK

- $D = 1.5 \text{ MGy}$
- $D_{degradation} = 5 \text{ MGy}$

Wu et al. (2013)

Transverse crack segmentation

3% UTS

6% UTS

9% UTS

12% UTS

200 μm

200 μm

RootPainter

Smith et al. (2022)

500 μm

Effect of ply configuration on transverse cracking

E- and S-glass fibre-reinforced epoxy observations

Conclusion

Time-resolved synchrotron
XMPI

Transverse cracking
in 4D

Promising data to
reconstruct

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